

A THEORETICAL METHOD OF DESCRIBING THE INTERACTION OF RAW COTTON WITH MOVING WORKING BODIES OF COTTON-CLEANING MACHINES

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Abstract

A theoretical regularity of the general behavior of raw cotton as a porous medium in the technological processes of its mechanical processing is substantiated for the first time. The speed of sound in a porous cotton medium is determined. The effect of additional force stresses inside the cotton medium, caused by the filtration of the air component from cotton raw materials during the introduction of the working body, is disclosed. A generalized equation is obtained that describes the force stress in a cotton medium when exposed to a variety of shapes of working bodies of cotton machines. A method for calculating the damage to seeds and cotton fibers in the process of interaction with the working bodies of processing machines is proposed.

In the process of processing raw cotton or cotton fiber, the fibrous mass is sharply mechanically affected by organs on the work of organs in the area of inflammation or disease, while complex processes occur inside the fibrous mass associated with a change in the measurement of density and pressure in it. Stresses in the fibers in the presence of conditions of high density of body mass, which can be manifested by plastic deformation, shortening of the fibers and severity of quality. The derived theory for the stress state of cotton raw materials in the process of processing allows to use it practically in all important issues of describing the damage of fiber and cotton seeds in the technological operations of primary processing of cotton.

Keywords: fiber damage, cotton seeds, sound speed, fiber cleaning, density of cotton raw materials.

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1. Introduction

The requirements for technological conditions of processing raw cotton are very diverse, and this in turn requires the development of a mathematical model of this kind of raw material [1, 2]. However, the absence of a general theoretical basis of the mechanics of the processes of the raw cotton interaction with the various working bodies of technological machines has led to the empirical way of development of technique and technology of the primary processing of raw cotton materials.

In the processes of cleaning, processing on cleaning machines, fibers and seeds of raw cotton undergo multiple dynamic changes [3, 4]. In practice, after the cleaning is completed, the fibers turn out to be significantly damaged, subject to deformations of the plastic limit and having lost physical and mechanical properties that are valuable for obtaining high-quality products.

The main reasons for these and other imperfections in the primary processing are the fact that during the design of cleaning machines and the establishment of technological processes, the basic physical, mechanical and other properties of raw cotton are basically neglected [5]. Research has not been completed in such fundamental directions as modeling the laws of deformation and shape change, the volume of raw cotton under the influence of static and dynamic loads. Existing models for calculating the design parameters of machines are often based on linear laws of mechanics. In contrast to the models of solids known in mechanics, which, under small deformations, obey linear laws, the mass of raw cotton only at very high densities can approach, viscoelastic media, in its law of deformation, [6, 7]. Obviously, the natural cotton mass is a heterogeneous, discrete and multicomponent medium, consisting, as it is known, of relatively short and randomly spaced fibers of different moisture, seeds, and extraneous impurities.

In the process of processing raw cotton or cotton fiber, the pulp undergoes mechanical impacts from the working bodies in the form of compression or tension, while complex processes occur inside the pulp that are associated with changes in the density of the raw material and

pressure in it [8, 9]. Stresses in the fibers under certain conditions reach critical values, which can lead to plastic deformation, shortening of the fiber and a decrease in quality.

The work [11] notes the fact that during the pressing of cotton at low speeds of the process, efforts are already manifested that accompany the compression and extrusion of air, which is in large quantities in the interfiber space of the cotton medium. These efforts are related to the speed of the process under consideration. Efforts of this kind can be associated with the plastic part of the total forces of deformation of the mass of raw materials.

It should be noted that the listed scientific works were mainly devoted to the static process of fiber compression in the mass in connection with their pressing into bales.

However, in these and other existing works, there is not enough data on the forces and stresses that arise inside the fibers during dynamic compression of the raw material mass, which cause deterioration or destruction of the fibers. Without knowledge of these stresses, it is impossible to plan the optimal technological process of processing, as well as to calculate the parameters of the working bodies of various machines.

The actual problem of studying the damage that occurs in the cotton mass during various operations during the technological processes of processing has been the subject of repeated studies by various authors.

2. Materials and methods of research

Let's consider the state of the fiber mass in the compression process with a conditional stamp. Similar conditions arise during the interaction of the feed rollers of ginning machines with cotton, the interaction of breeders and strands with grates, the interaction of the roller and the feeding table with fiber, etc. So, let's consider the effect of an elementary stamp on the fiber (**Fig. 1**).

Fig. 1. Movement of a cotton particle under the influence of an intruding stamp:
1 – stamp; 2 – raw cotton

As the starting point of our hypothesis, let's consider the motion of a homogeneous cotton mass as the motion of an ideal fluid with the subsequent introduction of conditions characterizing the difference between the pulp and the fluid.

The aim of this study is to determine the speed of penetration of the working body into the raw material, which can be small compared to the speed of sound in it, which leads to an increase in pressure and density, as well as an increase in the degree of mechanical microdamage of the raw materials that have arisen in contact with the solid surface of the working body.

As it is known, the steady one-dimensional motion of an ideal fluid or gas (without internal friction) can be described by the following differential equation (excluding weight) [10]:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x} = -\rho u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x}. \quad (1)$$

Here x is the coordinate of an arbitrary point A on the axis Ox , along which the medium moves; u is the velocity value of the material point of the liquid that passes through point A of space at time t ; ρ is the density of the medium at the point under consideration; p is the pressure assumed

to be the same for all directions at each point of the fluid. If the fluid is ideal and compressible, then in (1) the quantity ρ is variable.

For this case, the motion of a continuous compressible cotton mass, which has a variable density value, but which differs from an ideal fluid by the presence of internal friction, the pressure p is not the same in all directions. Therefore, it is necessary to introduce the following expression instead of the left side of (1):

$$\frac{\partial p_x}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial \sigma_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial \tau} + \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial z}, \quad (2)$$

where p_x is the pressure inside the cotton medium in the direction of the selected axis x .

From [7] it is known that the specific forces τ of internal friction in cotton are expressed as follows:

$$\tau = \mu \cdot P_b + G, \quad (3)$$

where P_b is the lateral pressure during cotton compaction; μ is the coefficient of internal friction of the material; G is the amount of total adhesion.

There is a pattern for lateral pressure P_b :

$$P_b = k \cdot p, \quad (4)$$

where k is the lateral pressure coefficient; p is the normal sealing load.

Let's consider now the problem of introducing a flat stamp, which further simulates a variety of working organs of machines, in a compressible flat layer of fiber.

From (3) and (4) it can be seen that the value of p and the internal tangent force τ are proportional to each other:

$$\tau = k_1 p, \quad (5)$$

where k_1 is the coefficient of proportionality.

It follows from (5) that:

$$\frac{\partial \tau}{\partial y} = k_1 \frac{\partial p}{\partial y}; \quad \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial z} = k_1 \frac{\partial p}{\partial z}. \quad (6)$$

From the point of view of fiber damage in the calculations for the stress p arising inside the cotton mass, the areas of its maximum area distribution (yz) are of the greatest interest (**Fig. 2**).

The condition for maximum stresses p , at the site (yz), leads to the fact that the following equation could be accepted:

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial y} = 0, \quad (7)$$

but, of course, for the x direction the magnitude $\partial p / \partial x \neq 0$.

According to (6) then it will be:

$$\frac{\partial \tau}{\partial y} = 0; \quad \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial z} = 0. \quad (8)$$

Thus, under the assumptions made, and taking into account (8), the quantity (2) is reduced to a single value:

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial \sigma_x}{\partial x}.$$

Now it can be seen that at the sites where p reaches the maximum (or minimum) value, it is possible to assume that the internal friction of the medium does not manifest itself. This means that

at such sites the motion of a non-ideal (with internal friction) medium is similar to the motion of an ideal (without internal friction).

Fig. 2. The scheme of power stresses in the cotton environment during the implementation of the working body

Cotton is a compressible viscous (with internal friction) medium. It should be noted that the issue of the motion of such an environment has been studied enough. Practical tasks for this kind of media are solved by combining the results obtained separately for an ideal compressible fluid and for a viscous incompressible fluid.

At subsonic flow rates, the general picture of flow past solids in a compressible viscous fluid is approximately the same as for an incompressible viscous fluid.

As already mentioned, in areas where the pressure p reaches a maximum (or minimum) value, it is quite possible to use the system of equations of motion for an ideal compressible fluid (gas) to describe the movement of the cotton mass.

Therefore, in the future, dynamic phenomena in a continuous squeezed-out medium such as cotton will be described by three equations that relate to each other such system parameters as the medium density ρ , pressure p , and the velocity u of the movement of particles of the medium [10]:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x}, \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(\rho u) = 0, \quad (10)$$

$$p = f(\rho). \quad (11)$$

Here (9) is the equation of one-dimensional motion; (10) is the equation of continuity of the medium; (11) is the equation of state relating pressure p and density ρ of the medium. The system of equations (9)–(11) allows to draw conclusions about the behavior of pressure p and density ρ for the cotton mass when the working bodies of processing machines are embedded into it.

3. Results and discussion

When the working bodies of machines are introduced into the cotton environment at a rate equal to the spread of sound in the medium, a sharp increase in pressure and density in the processed raw materials should be expected. This effect is one of the causes of damage to the natural components of raw cotton materials.

Let's show the mechanics of such a phenomenon for steady motion, when the addendum in (9) is $\partial u / \partial t = 0$. The value p in (9) is the stress inside the medium. If to consider p as pressure

from the working body on the raw materials, then now in (9) the sign of p will be the opposite. The equation (9) will look like this:

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = \rho u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x}. \quad (12)$$

Now let's multiply both sides of (12) by the value $\partial x / \partial \rho$, then let's obtain:

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial \rho} = \frac{\partial p}{\partial \rho} u \frac{\partial u}{\partial \rho}. \quad (13)$$

From the theory of acoustics, it is known that for small perturbations p and ρ , the quantity:

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial \rho} = c^2. \quad (14)$$

The left side of (13) is the square of the velocity with sound vibrations of the medium. With that said, let's rewrite (13) in the following form:

$$\frac{\partial p}{\rho} = \frac{1}{c^2} u \frac{\partial u}{\partial \rho}, \quad (15)$$

and let's assume that in the last expression the quantity p changes little, so that $\rho = \rho_0 + \rho_1$, where ρ_0 is a constant, and ρ_1 is a small first-order quantity. Then in (15), one can use series expansion for a small quantity ρ_1 / ρ_0 :

$$\frac{1}{\rho} = \frac{1}{\rho_0} \left(1 + \frac{\rho_1}{\rho_0} \right)^{-1} = \frac{1}{\rho_0} \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1}{\rho_0} + \dots \right).$$

Taking into account the last expression, the left-hand side of (15) takes the form:

$$\frac{\partial p}{\rho} = \frac{\partial p}{\rho_0} \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1}{\rho_0} \right) = \frac{\partial p}{\rho_0}, \quad (16)$$

where the product of quantities is omitted from consideration $\partial p \cdot \rho_1$ as a second-order quantity of smallness.

If to substitute the last result from (16) into the left-hand side of (15) and integrate the expression obtained, then:

$$\rho = \frac{1}{2} \rho_0 \left(\frac{u}{c} \right)^2 + \text{const.} \quad (17)$$

Here, for $u = 0$, the integration constant $\text{const} = \rho_0$ is the initial density of the system, and it finally follows from (17) that the dependence of the density ρ on the ratio u/c is:

$$\rho = \rho_0 \left[1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{u}{c} \right)^2 \right]. \quad (18)$$

If to substitute further the found expression (18) for the density ρ in (12), then this equation will take the following form:

$$dp = \rho_0 \left[1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{u}{c} \right)^2 \right] u du. \quad (19)$$

After integration (19), let's obtain that the value of pressure p is:

$$p = \frac{\rho_0 u^2}{2} \left[1 + \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{u}{c} \right)^2 \right] + \text{const.} \quad (20)$$

Here, for $u=0$, the integration constant $\text{const} = p_0$ is the initial pressure in the system, and then from (20):

$$p - p_0 = \Delta p = \frac{\rho_0 u^2}{2} \left[1 + \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{u}{c} \right)^2 \right]. \quad (21)$$

From (21) it is seen, that the addendum in square brackets is a correction for compressibility. For example, at speed, when $u = c$, let's obtain:

$$1 + \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{u}{c} \right)^2 = 1 + \frac{1}{4} = 1.25.$$

Taking compressibility into account gives a correction for p of 25 %. With a more accurate calculation, this correction will be 32 %.

In the same way, in (18), the addendum in square brackets reflects the degree of compaction of the medium. When $u = c$, it will be:

$$1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{u}{c} \right)^2 = 1 + \frac{1}{2} = 1.5.$$

Here, taking into account the compressibility gives a correction for the density ρ of 50 %. A more accurate calculation shows that the correction will be 60 %.

When the working bodies of cotton-processing machines are introduced into raw materials on the surface of organs, there are such sites K (points) on which the lines of trajectories of particles of incoming raw materials are perpendicular to the surface of the working body (**Fig. 3**). At such sites, the raw material particles are completely inhibited, their speed is zero, here the total pressure p_k is maximal.

Fig. 3. Scheme of introducing a machine organ into cotton raw materials:
1 – working body of the machine; 2 – cotton medium

It is known that when a solid body flows around an ideal incompressible liquid (gas), the pressure p_k at the critical point K , where the flow is inhibited, is equal to the total pressure of the flow:

$$p_k = p_0 + q_0.$$

Here,

$$q_0 = \frac{\rho_0 u^2}{2},$$

velocity head of incompressible fluid (gas) flow; p_0 is initial static pressure in the medium.

When a solid body flows around by an ideal compressible liquid (gas) with a subsonic flow velocity, the pressure at the critical point K is p_k , and according to (21):

$$p_k = p_0 + \left[1 + \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{u}{c} \right)^2 \right],$$

is greater than the total pressure $p_0 + q_0$ of the flow, and an excess pressure at the critical point K equal to more than $p_k - p_0$ is greater than the pressure head q_0 , and the difference between the excess pressure and the velocity head will be as great as the ratio for a given flow u/c .

In [10], it was noted that the temperature T_k at the critical point of zero velocity can be found from:

$$\frac{T_k}{T_0} = 1 + \frac{k-1}{2} \left(\frac{u}{c} \right)^2. \quad (22)$$

Here, T_0 is the initial temperature of the medium; k is an indicator of the adiabatic compression of the medium. As a first approximation, it is possible to take $k=3$ for the cotton medium, since for the subsonic motion the usual adiabatic dependence between pressure and density can be used. Then,

$$T_k = T_0 \left[1 + \left(\frac{u}{c} \right)^2 \right].$$

If, $u = c$ then,

$$1 + \left(\frac{u}{c} \right)^2 = 1 + 1 = 2,$$

and the temperature rises to $T_k = 2T_0$.

Let's note that the results of (18), (21), (22) are valid only at a flow velocity u not exceeding the speed of sound c in the medium.

At a velocity u exceeding c , an abrupt change in the parameters p , ρ , u , T occurs and the continuity of the change in the indicated characteristics is violated, and the flow velocity decreases. Pressure, density and temperature rise sharply.

Experiments of a dynamic nature were carried out to simulate the process of introducing the splitter's riot pins into raw cotton. For this, an experimental setup was developed.

In the experiments, a peg of a round cross section with a diameter of 12 mm was used in two versions. In the first version, the peg was bent along its axis. The bend of the top part of the peg was made along the radius mm, which corresponds to the angle (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Geometrical shape of the pegs:
1 – straight pegs of round section; 2 – pegs of curved round section

The procedure for conducting experiments on the setup was as follows. The peg was installed in front of the slot of the seal box and the rotation drive was turned on. When the peg was introduced into the compacted cotton, the forces were measured, and when the peg left the disassembly zone, the drive of the working body was turned off.

For a theoretical analysis of the dynamics of the penetration of the pin into the cotton mass, the results of the cotton deformation forces acting in the normal direction were used.

For a cotton environment, it is assumed that it is a two-component mixture of cotton fibers and air included in the spaces between them. The air component of such an environment in processing operations is involved in an interconnected process of changing density and pressure. The air enclosed inside the raw material does not have time to completely go outside at the moment the working body is introduced into the environment. This fact has an impact on the dynamics of technological processes and damage to the fibers of the raw material.

With the static nature of the loading of the medium, the rate of air filtration from it is very small, and the force effect of such an outflow is negligible. However, under dynamic loading of an array of raw cotton, the exit of air from the medium is limited in time, and part of the external efforts from the working body will already be perceived by the air layer.

Table 1 shows the results of experiments on the forces P_g of dynamic penetration.

Table 1

Results of experiments on the forces P_g of dynamic penetration

Pin shape	The value of the dynamic force P_g , H, recorded by the sensors							
	distance L , mm from pin to sensor							
	110	95	80	65	50	35	20	2
Pegs of straight round section	0.09	0.30	0.70	1.20	2.5	3.70	5.00	6.80
Pegs of curved round section	0.09	0.17	0.60	0.90	2.1	3.00	4.00	5.00

The cotton medium has an essential compressibility property. At the introduction rates into the raw cotton of the working bodies of processing machines commensurate with the speed of sound propagation in such an environment, one should expect, according to the derived ratio (18), (21), (22), a significant increase in the density, pressure and temperature, raw materials in the areas adjacent to the surface of the working bodies. The maximum increase in environmental parameters (at subsonic speeds) compared with their initial values can reach at $u = c$ the values: for density ρ by 1.6 raa, for pressure p by 1.3 times, for temperature T by 2 times.

Along with the study of traditional methods of cleaning raw cotton from weed impurities, the search continues for new ones that provide, with a significant cleaning effect, the maximum preservation of the quality of the fibrous material.

The development of the theoretical foundations for feeding cotton gins, the mechanics of the process of interaction of raw cotton with the working bodies of the purifier will create an actual direction in the study of cleaning processes, lay the scientific foundations for the design of purifiers, identify areas for searching for new processes and technological schemes for cleaning cotton.

Such a local sharp increase in the characteristics of the cotton medium is a significant cause of fiber damage.

It follows from this that when assigning a technological mode of processing it is necessary to measure it with the value of sound speed for a given density of raw materials.

Implementation at such speed rate of working bodies into raw materials that are comparable to the speed of sound at a given density of raw materials should be avoided. In addition, the actual cotton mass is very heterogeneous in density, and can vary significantly in a small volume from the nominal average density in the total volume. Further studies show that an increase in the density of raw materials within certain limits leads to a decrease in the speed of sound. At a density of $0 < p < 350 \text{ kg/m}^3$, the speed of sound lies in the range $330 > s > 30 \text{ m/s}$.

If lumps of increased density are found in raw materials, then the probability of their damage is greater in comparison with the main less dense mass of processed raw materials, since the

speed of sound in dense lumps is relatively low compared to the main medium. The conclusion is that the raw materials should be as homogeneous as possible in density. This reduces fiber damage.

From the numerical results for the speed of sound, a curve is constructed of its dependence on the mixture density $c = f(\rho)$ in Fig. 4, 5.

Based on the numerical results of the experiment, a curve of its dependence on the density of the mixture $c = f(\rho)$ was plotted for the speed of sound in Fig. 4, 5.

Fig. 5. The curve of the speed sound dependence c on the density ρ of raw cotton materials

An analysis of the results for the speed of sound in the cotton mass shows that starting from for air without fiber impurities, this speed subsequently drops sharply in value even with a small amount of cotton fiber in the mixture.

So with a fiber content of 5 kg in 1 m^3 of the mixture, the speed of sound is $c = 150$ m/s, and with a fiber content of 25 kg in 1 m^3 of the mixture the speed of sound $c = 73$ m/s. The minimum value for c lies in the range of values $c = 21-24$ m/s for a wide range of raw material densities $\rho = 300-900$ kg/m^3 .

Thus, the speed of sound in the two-component cotton medium studied turns out to be significantly less than in each of the two components in (air $c = 330$ m/s and cotton fiber $c = 1700$ m/s) taken separately.

When transporting raw cotton with the pneumatic method, it is recommended to choose a speed limit that minimizes damage to the fibers.

The results obtained will be used in all transitions of the technological process of processing raw cotton.

5. Conclusions

The specificity of the research is that the cotton mass is considered as a compressible porous two-component medium consisting of a mixture of cotton fibers and air included in the gap between them. The influence of air included in the composition of the porous medium is essential in dynamic processing processes, and it must be taken into account when planning technological modes.

It has been theoretically and experimentally determined that the speed of sound in a mixture and air is relatively low, compared with the speed of sound and linearly oriented fibers (threads), where it is 1700 m/s. When the density of raw materials $\rho = 250-300$ kg/m^3 , the theoretically found speed of sound is 24–28 m/s, and the experimentally determined speed is 50–60 m/s.

When instilling the working bodies of processing machines into the cotton environment, one should expect the appearance of the compressibility of the medium. This significantly increases the pressure, density and temperature in the raw cotton. This effect is described by a system of three equations that interconnect the pressure, density and velocity of particles of a compressible medium.

The speed of instilling of the working body into the raw material medium may be small compared to the speed of sound in it, however, the local filtration rate of the air component on the surface of the working body may be comparable with the speed of sound, which leads to an

increase in pressure and density, as well as an increase in the degree of mechanical micro damage to raw materials arising from contact with the solid surface of the working body.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on reasonable request.

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